

Analyzing the consequences of postponing electricity subsidy reforms in Iran: A retrospective study

Siab Mamipour^{a,*}, Mahsa Ghahremani^b, Ata Malfuzi^c, Seyed Armin Motahar^d

^a Faculty of Economics, Kharazmi University, Tehran, Iran

^b Department of Economics, University of New Brunswick, Fredericton, NB, Canada

^c Department of Economics, Simon Fraser University, Burnaby, BC, Canada

^d Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Duisburg-Essen, Essen, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Handling Editor: Dr. Mark Howells

Keywords:

Electricity subsidies
Energy reform
Consumption behavior
Elasticity
State-space modeling

ABSTRACT

Iran, as an oil-revenue-based economy, remains one of the world's largest providers of fossil fuel subsidies, with the electricity sector receiving the greatest share. This sustained support has driven per-capita electricity consumption to grow by 5 % annually, significantly above the global average. To assess the economic and behavioral effects of delayed subsidy reforms on consumption patterns and demand elasticities, a state-space model was applied across five phased scenarios spanning 1985–2023. Results reveal pronounced temporal variation in both price and income elasticities: subsidies have dampened consumer responsiveness and entrenched reliance on low-cost energy. All reform scenarios demonstrate a positive relationship between tariff increases and price elasticity, underscoring the necessity of gradual, stepwise subsidy removal. Delays in reform not only heighten the government's fiscal burden but also weaken price elasticities and undermine the effectiveness of subsequent measures. Accordingly, we recommend a five-year, phased reform plan—with targeted support measures for vulnerable households—to steer electricity consumption toward greater efficiency and equity.

1. Introduction

Energy subsidies play a critical role in addressing price volatility and inflation volatility in many developing countries, including Iran. Initially introduced to stabilize markets, these subsidies gradually evolved into broader social protection mechanisms as governments sought to shield vulnerable populations from price shocks [1].

In Iran, government intervention in commodity markets dates back to 1932, when silo construction and above-market wheat procurement were used to support farmers. Since then, subsidies have become a key policy tool for pursuing objectives such as income redistribution. However, extensive subsidy programs have also distorted market equilibrium and undermined efficient resource allocation in energy sectors.

The electricity sector is among the most heavily subsidized in Iran. Despite various reform initiatives—most notably those outlined in the Fifth Development Plan (2011–2015)—Iran remains the world's largest provider of energy subsidies, with electricity alone accounting for \$25 billion in 2023, or 11.4 % of global electricity subsidies (Fig. 1).

This substantial fiscal commitment has driven per-capita electricity consumption to surge unsustainably. Between 1985 and 2023, consumption rose from 0.64 MWh to 3.9 MWh per person—an average annual increase of 5 %, two to three times the global rate (Fig. 2a) [3,4]. Although a tariff hike in 2011 temporarily reduced usage by 1.5 % (Fig. 2b), the reform was then postponed and demand quickly rebounded. These trends underscore that, without comprehensive subsidy restructuring to restore accurate price signals, managing electricity demand effectively remains a formidable challenge.

While numerous studies have explored electricity demand and the socio-economic effects of subsidy removal, few have addressed the dynamic costs of delaying reforms or modeled the time-varying nature of consumer price elasticity. This represents a critical gap, as price and income elasticities are not static. Persistent subsidies can entrench inefficient, energy-intensive consumption behaviors that become less responsive to policy interventions over time—particularly in the short run. Therefore, assuming fixed elasticities before and after reform, as many earlier studies have done, risks underestimating or

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: s.mamipour@khu.ac.ir (S. Mamipour), mahsa.ghahremani@unb.ca (M. Ghahremani), atamalfuzi@gmail.com (A. Malfuzi), seyed.motahar@stud.uni-due.de (S.A. Motahar).

¹ Permanent address: Kharazmi University: No.43.Taleghani Ave, Tehran, Postal Code: 15719-14911, I.R. Iran.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2025.101889>

Received 12 January 2025; Received in revised form 6 August 2025; Accepted 7 September 2025

Available online 17 September 2025

2211-467X/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Fig. 1. World energy subsidies and Iran's share, 2024 [2].

misrepresenting the true effects of subsidy restructuring.

Given this shortcoming in literature, the significance of this study lies in capturing the temporal evolution of electricity demand in response to reform policies, particularly under scenarios involving phased or postponed implementation. Iran serves as a relevant and instructive case due to its long-standing history of energy subsidies and repeated—but often incomplete—attempts at reform. Understanding how consumer responsiveness changes over time in such contexts is essential for crafting effective, realistic, and politically viable energy policies.

This study addresses these gaps by analyzing electricity subsidy reforms in Iran across multiple time horizons and quantifying the economic consequences of delaying reform. In contrast to previous work that treats demand elasticities as fixed, this research explicitly models how both price and income elasticities evolve over time, providing a more realistic framework for assessing the impacts of subsidy reform on electricity consumption and fiscal sustainability.

Accordingly, the study is guided by the following research questions.

- How have electricity price and income elasticities in Iran evolved over time?

Fig. 2. Trends in electricity consumption in Iran and the world [3,4].

- What are the economic effects of subsidy reforms in Iran's electricity sector?
- What are the costs associated with delaying the implementation of these reforms?

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a literature review, Section 3 discusses the methodology, Section 4 presents the empirical findings, and Section 5 outlines the conclusions and policy recommendations.

2. Literature review

In recent years, energy subsidy reform has emerged as one of the most prominent policy challenges in many developing countries. These reforms—particularly in the electricity sector—carry significant economic, social, and environmental implications and are often accompanied by complex behavioral and institutional challenges. Over the past decades, a substantial body of literature has developed to analyze the impacts of such reforms. Appendix Table A summarizes these studies, categorized by methodology and country. Broadly, literature can be divided into two main groups: studies focusing on macroeconomic and distributional outcomes, and those analyzing electricity demand behavior and price elasticities.

The first group of studies primarily employs Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models or Input-Output frameworks to assess the effects of subsidy removal or adjustment on GDP, employment, income distribution, and emissions. For example, studies such as [5–8], and [9] indicate that subsidy reforms often reduce energy demand and carbon emissions but may also lead to short-term negative effects on GDP and the welfare of vulnerable groups. Study [10], using a hybrid CGE and Input-Output model for Iran and the GCC countries, highlights the complexities arising from cross-subsidization among different energy carriers. In the case of Iran, studies [11,12] evaluate various pricing reform scenarios and assess their impacts on both welfare and environmental indicators. Similarly, study [13], using an Input-Output approach, finds that the effects of subsidy removal vary significantly depending on the type of energy carrier and household consumption patterns.

The second group of research focuses on electricity consumption behavior, with an emphasis on estimating price and income elasticities across countries. Several studies adopt classical econometric methods such as ARDL ([14,15]), panel data models ([16,17]), or micro-level approaches ([18]), generally assuming constant elasticities over time. The overall findings suggest that electricity demand tends to be price-inelastic in the short run but may become more responsive in the long run as consumers adjust their behavior.

More recently, State Space Models (SSMs) have gained traction for the dynamic analysis of electricity demand. These models allow for the estimation of time-varying elasticities and are particularly well-suited for capturing shifts in consumer behavior in response to price shocks or policy interventions. Studies such as [19–21], and [22] demonstrate that price responsiveness can evolve over time. For instance, study [21] finds that in Lesotho, consumer sensitivity to electricity prices increases in the long term. However, in the case of Iran, relatively few studies have employed this framework. Most existing research relies on point estimates of elasticities and does not capture their evolution over time.

From a methodological perspective, each approach has distinct advantages and limitations. CGE models are effective for assessing long-term, economy-wide effects but require extensive data and rely on strong assumptions, such as fully rational agents and market-clearing behavior. Traditional models such as ARDL and panel data regressions are suitable for estimating static relationships but assume time-invariant elasticities. In contrast, State Space Models offer a flexible structure that captures gradual changes in consumer behavior, market dynamics, and the delayed effects of policy implementation.

Despite the extensive literature, a critical gap remains: most studies

assume that consumer responses to price are static over time and fail to account for the economic costs of delays in reform implementation. This study aims to address this gap by using a State Space modeling framework to estimate the long-term, time-varying price and income elasticities of electricity demand in Iran. Additionally, it quantifies the economic costs associated with delays in implementing electricity price reforms.

3. Methodology

3.1. Model and scenarios

The estimation of energy demand has been approached through various modeling techniques, including Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models, Input-Output models, and econometric methods. Although CGE models are frequently applied in energy policy analysis due to their ability to capture general equilibrium effects across sectors, they rely on strong assumptions such as perfect competition, market clearing, and fully rational agents. Moreover, they typically assume static or pre-defined behavioral parameters. In contrast, the State Space Model (SSM), adopted in this study, allows for a more flexible and dynamic representation of sector-specific behavior, particularly suitable for analyzing time-varying elasticities and gradual adjustments in electricity demand. This feature is especially relevant in the context of electricity subsidy reforms, where behavioral responses may evolve over time and are often subject to policy-induced shocks. Consequently, the analysis emphasizes the strengths of SSM in modeling demand responses over time under evolving policy conditions.

Originally developed in control engineering during the 1960s, the state-space concept has recently found application in economics [23, 24]. SSM incorporates observation and transition equations and offers two key advantages. Firstly, it models and estimates unobserved variables such as economic activity, pricing regulations, structural changes, and price levels. Another significant advantage is its capacity to handle parameter instability and time-varying coefficients. The Hansen test is utilized prior to estimation to confirm the changing coefficients over time [25]. Consequently, when deriving the demand function, we employ time-varying parameters based on the Kalman Filter² to derive more accurate coefficients. The choice of SSM over CGE models aligns with the study's primary objective—capturing the evolving nature of price and income elasticities under subsidy reforms. Unlike CGE models, which generally rely on fixed elasticity parameters and equilibrium assumptions, the SSM enables continuous tracking of elasticity changes, identification of structural breaks, and incorporation of short-term adjustments in consumer behavior, making it better suited for assessing the dynamic consequences of delaying reforms.

The electricity demand function utilized in this study is derived from several sources, namely [20,22,26–29]. Equation (1) illustrates this demand function for electricity consumption, which considers real income and the real price of electricity.

$$\ln(EC_t) = \beta_{0t} + \beta_1 \ln(EC_{t-1}) + \beta_{2t} \ln(EP_t) + \beta_{3t} \ln(GDP_t) + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

$$\beta_{st} = \Phi\beta_{st-1} + e_t \quad (2)$$

Equation (1) is known as the observation (or measurement) equation, and the state equation is Equation (2) where $\ln EC_t$ is an observed variable and β_{st} is a state variable.

EC is the electricity consumption in TWh; EC_{t-1} is the first lag of electricity consumption to capture consumption habits; EP is the real electricity price in Rials/kWh, and GDP is the real income in Billion Rials. All data are depicted in their natural logarithmic form. The coefficients for the real electricity price and GDP , as determined by the

² An algorithm that provides estimations of some unidentified variables given the measurements observed over time [23].

Kalman Filter, exhibit time-varying characteristics in this investigation. The parameter ϕ in Equation (2) represents the persistence or inertia of the time-varying coefficients, indicating how the elasticities from the previous period influence their values in the current period. Economically, ϕ captures the gradual adjustment process of consumer responses to changes in electricity prices and income, thereby reflecting the dynamic evolution of demand elasticities over time. The coefficient β_1 reflects the persistence in habit establishment, indicating that current consumption tendencies are influenced by previous consumption levels. Furthermore, it is assumed that β_1 remains constant over time.

The coefficients β_2 and β_3 vary over time, denoting the elasticity of electricity prices and income, respectively. The research period covers from 1985 to 2023, in which a retrospective method is used to modify electricity subsidies. Various scenarios were analyzed to investigate the changes in electricity subsidy mechanisms:

- i. Reference scenario: lack of reform in electricity subsidy and continuation of current subsidy system.
- ii. Phasing out subsidies in 1995 (POS 1995): gradual elimination of electricity subsidies over a five-year period (1995–2000) and complete removal by 2000.
- iii. Phasing out subsidies in 2000 (POS 2000): gradual reduction of electricity subsidies over a five-year period (2000–2005) and complete elimination by 2005.
- iv. Phasing out subsidies in 2005 (POS 2005): step-by-step reduction of electricity subsidies over five years (2005–2010) leading to complete removal by 2010.
- v. Phasing out subsidies in 2010 (POS 2010): gradual decrease in electricity subsidies over a five-year period (2010–2015) culminating in their complete elimination by 2015.
- vi. Phasing out subsidies in 2015 (POS 2015): systematic reduction of electricity subsidies over a five-year period (2015–2020) and complete elimination by 2020.

This study examined the disparity between the production cost and selling price of electricity used as a subsidy in different scenarios. Fig. 3 illustrates the subsidy amount granted on electricity prices. The introduction of subsidy reforms could lead to varying outcomes because of changes in electricity subsidies duration. The convergence of distinct subsidy scenarios is depicted in Fig. 3.

The Iranian government introduced energy subsidy reforms as part of the initial national development program launched in 1990 [30]. In Fig. 3, the deviation in electricity prices is depicted across five scenarios phasing out subsidies (POS) compared to the historical (reference) scenario.

Over time, changes in the price elasticity of electricity suggest that consumer sensitivity to price changes is not constant. Therefore, it is essential to estimate the connection between electricity prices and own-price elasticity by extracting the price elasticity trend in a particular reference scenario. By discerning the influence of electricity prices on own-price elasticity, it becomes possible to accurately assess demand elasticity in various subsidy reform situations. As subsidies are phased out and prices increase in scenarios POS1995, POS2000, POS2005, POS2010 and POS2015 the price elasticity of demand will deviate from that in the reference scenario, requiring a reassessment. Thus, the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model³ is employed to identify the relationship between the price and the price elasticity of demand Equation (3).

$$\beta_{2t}^{base} = \mu + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i \beta_{2t-i}^{base} + \sum_{j=0}^q \gamma_j \ln \left(EP_{t-j}^{base} \right) + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

³ The ARDL model was developed by Ref. [31]. One of the advantages of this model is that it has consistent estimates of long-term coefficient regardless of whether they are stationary or non-stationary series in a regression [32].

In the initial stage of the analysis, Equation (3) is formulated based on the reference (base) scenario. The coefficients obtained from computing price elasticity within the context of the subsidy reform scenario are then employed in Equation (4). Subsequently, these coefficients are utilized in Equation (4) for further analysis.

$$\hat{\beta}_{2t}^{POS} = \hat{\mu} + \sum_{i=1}^p \hat{\delta}_i \beta_{2t-i}^{POS} + \sum_{j=0}^q \hat{\gamma}_j \ln \left(EP_{t-j}^{POS} \right) \quad (4)$$

The POS presents a range of scenarios for phasing out electricity subsidies over varying time frames. These scenarios outline different approaches for reducing electricity subsidies, culminating in the final stage where the electricity demand under each subsidy elimination scenario is calculated using Equation (5).

$$\ln(\widehat{EC}_t^{POS}) = \hat{\beta}_{0t} + \hat{\beta}_1 \ln(EC_{t-1}) + \hat{\beta}_{2t}^{POS} \ln(EP_t^{POS}) + \hat{\beta}_{3t} \ln(GDP_t) \quad (5)$$

The actual value of electricity consumption between 1985 and 2023 was determined by the subsidy prices in the reference scenario. Despite the known relationship between prices and price elasticity, an increase in electricity prices as part of subsidy reform efforts may result in biased outcomes. Therefore, it is crucial for price elasticity to adjust to changes in electricity prices (due to subsidy reforms) and the estimated electricity demand. According to consumer behavior theory, there exists a link between price and own-price elasticity within a linear demand function, implying that the sensitivity to price variations rises with the demand price (Fig. 4).

In the reference scenario, the real electricity price remains low, and sustaining subsidies could lead to a perfectly inelastic outcome ($\varepsilon = 0$). However, if policymakers aim to gradually reform and phase out subsidies, the price elasticity will rise. This research estimates the point-price elasticity of demand using the SSM across various years. Consequently, under the subsidy reform scenarios, the point-price elasticity will be adjusted when there is an increase in electricity prices in a specific year, making its utilization challenging before the initiation of any subsidy reforms. Therefore, the point-price elasticity of demand is initially estimated for price changes through the ARDL model, followed by the calculation of electricity demand. It is important to note that the analysis of price subsidy reforms is conducted under the ceteris paribus assumption.

3.2. Data

Data on electricity consumption, real electricity prices, and real GDP used in this research were obtained from the Central Bank [34] and the energy balance sheet of Iran [35] covering the period from 1985 to 2023. All monetary values, including electricity prices and GDP, are expressed in constant 2011 prices, adjusted using the Consumer Price Index (CPI) published by the Central Bank of Iran.

Fig. 5 visually depicts the fluctuation in real electricity prices in Iran, indicating a consistent downward trajectory punctuated by spikes in 1994 and 2011, primarily attributed to temporary subsidy initiatives. Iran's policymakers, leveraging considerable oil revenue, historically endeavored to stabilize energy prices and subsidize various forms of energy, including electricity, over the past four decades. Maintaining nominal prices amidst high inflationary pressures contributed to the gradual decline in real electricity prices over time. The resultant decrease in the real cost of electricity facilitated a notable surge in consumption levels, escalating from 30.8 TWh in 1985 to 333 TWh in 2023, marking an over ten-fold increase over a 39-year period. In contrast, the country's real GDP exhibited a 2.5-fold increase during the same duration, as illustrated in Fig. 6.

The descriptive statistics for the variables are detailed in Table 1. It is evident from the data that the real price of electricity in Iran experienced a yearly average decrease of 1.8 %, primarily attributed to the presence of electricity subsidies. Conversely, average electricity consumption and

Fig. 3. Electricity subsidies and POS scenarios (Authors' calculations and [3]).

Fig. 4. Price elasticity of demand (Authors' illustration).

real incomes demonstrated increases of 6.6 % and 2.6 %, respectively.

4. Empirical results

As outlined in the methodology section, the Hansen test is utilized to evaluate parameter instability in determining the most optimal and efficient SSM. The findings are presented in Table 2. The null hypothesis posits that parameters remain constant and stable throughout the specified period. The test results reveal a test statistic of 0.67, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This rejection signifies that the parameters exhibit instability and vary across time.

4.1. Estimation of electricity demand in the reference scenario

Table 3 presents the estimation results obtained from the Kalman Filter. The coefficient β_1 indicates that past electricity consumption significantly influences current consumption patterns. The time-varying coefficients β_{0t} , β_{2t} , and β_{3t} represent the intercept, price elasticity, and income elasticity, respectively. The estimated price elasticity of demand is negative and less than one, consistent with demand theory and indicating that electricity demand is inelastic. Meanwhile, the income elasticity is positive but below one, suggesting that electricity is considered a normal (essential) good in Iran. The coefficients reported in Table 3 correspond to the final state values from the Kalman Filter for the year 2023. To capture the dynamic nature of consumer responses

Fig. 5. Trends in electricity consumption and real electricity prices [33,34].

Fig. 6. Trends in electricity consumption and real GDP [33,34].

Table 1
Data on descriptive statistics (1985–2023).

Variable	Unit	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	AAGR ^d (%)
Electricity consumption (EC)	TWh	143.4	91.8	30.8	333.0	6.6
Real electricity price (EP)	Rials/kWh	773.8	263.2	263.2	1319.2	-1.8
Real GDP (GDP)	Trillion Rials	4732.3	1490.3	2349.0	7003.0	2.6

^a AAGR: Average Annual Growth Rate. Source: Authors' calculations.

Table 2
Hansen test results for parameter stability.

Series	LnEC, LnPE, LnGDP
Null hypothesis	Parameters are stable
Lc statistic	0.67
p-value	0.04
Inference	Parameters are not stable (Null hypothesis rejected at the 5 % level)

Source: Authors' calculations

Table 3
Kalman Filter estimation results (1985–2023).

Variables	Estimated coefficients	z-Statistics
β_1 (lag of electricity consumption)	0.94	23.3 *
	Final state	
β_0 (intercept)	-0.32	-2.20 **
β_2 (price elasticity)	-0.01	-0.93
β_3 (income elasticity)	0.09	6.99 *
Log likelihood	56.89	
Akaike info criterion	-2.89	
Schwarz criterion	-2.80	
Hannan-Quinn criterion	-2.85	
Normality test: Jarque-Bera (prob)	0.39 (0.82)	

*, **, *** significant levels at 1 %, 5 %, and 10 %, respectively.

Source: Authors' calculations

more comprehensively, the time-varying trajectories of price and income elasticities have been estimated and are clearly illustrated in Fig. 8, demonstrating substantial variation throughout the study period.

Moreover, the residuals of the model passed the Jarque-Bera normality test (prob. = 0.82), confirming that they are normally distributed and lending support to the reliability of the model's statistical inference. In Fig. 7, the estimated (fitted) values for electricity

consumption are compared with their actual values, illustrating that the estimated electricity demand function effectively explains the actual electricity consumption. The annual estimates of price and income elasticities can be found in Fig. 8. Furthermore, the price elasticity observed in 2023 suggests that the maintenance of price subsidies in the electricity sector has lessened consumers' responsiveness to price fluctuations over time. In 2023, the price elasticity pertaining to electricity demand was minimal and insignificant.

As illustrated in Fig. 8, the estimation results derived from the state-space model (SSM) reveal that both price and income elasticities of electricity demand exhibit significant temporal variation. The income elasticity findings confirm that electricity is generally perceived as a necessity good, its consumption tends to rise with increasing income. However, this responsiveness weakens over time. The declining income elasticity can be explained by several interrelated factors. First, the saturation effect suggests that once households or firms reach a certain level of electricity consumption necessary for their basic or productive needs, further income growth leads to relatively smaller increases in usage. Second, structural changes in the Iranian economy, such as a gradual transition from energy-intensive sectors (e.g., manufacturing) to less energy-dependent sectors (e.g., services and technology), have likely shifted consumption patterns, reducing the overall sensitivity of electricity demand to income fluctuations. Furthermore, technological advancements, particularly improvements in the energy efficiency of appliances, buildings, and industrial processes—may have contributed to a decoupling of electricity use from income growth. Lastly, policy interventions, including subsidy reforms and pricing regulations, may have also played a role by altering consumption incentives and promoting more efficient use.

In contrast, the results regarding price elasticity indicate a declining responsiveness of electricity demand to price changes over time, with elasticity approaching zero in later years. This pattern coincides with the long-term decline in real electricity prices, as shown in Fig. 9. Under the ceteris paribus assumption, when prices are kept artificially low due to subsidies, consumers become less sensitive to price signals, leading to near-zero elasticity. The analysis further reveals a direct correlation between price elasticity and real electricity prices, suggesting that responsiveness increases when prices rise and declines when prices are suppressed. These dynamics underscore the importance of price reforms in restoring the signaling function of electricity prices within demand-side management strategies.

4.2. Results of the subsidy reform scenarios

In accordance with the methodology outlined, five different electricity subsidy reform scenarios were assessed across varying time frames to explore the repercussions of implementation delays. To accomplish this, it is crucial to regard the price elasticity of electricity

Fig. 7. Actual and fitted values of electricity consumption (Source: Authors' calculations).

Fig. 8. Price and income elasticity in the Reference Scenario (Source: Authors' calculations).

demand as an endogenous variable. The findings from Equation (3) for the baseline scenario are detailed in Table 4. The estimation of the price elasticity of demand is carried out through the utilization of ARDL model. Furthermore, a dummy variable has been incorporated for the year 1990 to address the assumption of normally distributed residuals. The ARDL (3, 2) analysis affirms that the formulated model effectively accounts for 97 % of the variations observed in the price elasticity of electricity.

Fig. 10a depicts the variations in the real price of electricity across five electricity subsidy reform scenarios, while consumer response or sensitivity to these price adjustments is demonstrated in Fig. 10b. The Figures indicate that subsidy reforms result in heightened price elasticities and decreased electricity usage. Furthermore, the timing of the reforms plays a crucial role in influencing the extent of the impact on price elasticity.

Analyzing the POS1995 and POS2015 scenarios indicates that

Fig. 9. Electricity prices versus price elasticity (Source: Authors' calculations).

Table 4
Result of ARDL (3,2) for price elasticity.

Variable	Coefficient	t-statistic
intercept	0.087	6.055 *
β_{t-1}	0.809	21.06 *
β_{2t-1}	-0.081	-9.757 *
β_{3t-1}	-0.049	-10.843 *
$\ln PE_t$	-0.011	-3.908 **
$\ln PE_{t-1}$	0.005	1.4523 ***
$\ln PE_{t-2}$	-0.010	-3.694 *
Dum 1990	-0.027	-9.511 *
Sample		1985–2023
Adjusted R-squared		0.97
F-statistic		106.4 (0.0000)
Residual normality test: Jarque-Bera		1.79 (0.408)
serial correlation test: Breusch-Godfrey LM		0.627 (0.543)
Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey		0.825 (0.575)

*, **, *** significant levels at 1 %, 5 %, and 10 %, respectively. P-values in parentheses.

Source: Authors' calculations

postponing the implementation of subsidy reforms will result in a lesser impact on price elasticity. Prolonged subsidies lead to a decrease in price elasticity towards zero, diminishing consumer responsiveness to changes in prices. As shown in Fig. 11, the demand point-price elasticity for the initial reform plan of POS1995 is double that of the reference scenario, implying that the timely initiation of subsidy reforms could significantly enhance the management of electricity consumption.

As the price elasticity of demand is consistently less than one for all scenarios, the reduction in electricity usage is proportionally less than the increase in price resulting from subsidy reforms. The delay in implementing the subsidy has a minor impact on controlling electricity consumption due to the reduced-price elasticity of electricity. Conversely, earlier subsidy reforms lead to more effective control over electricity usage. Analysis of subsidy reform scenarios from 1985 to 2023 reveals that electricity consumption decreased by 17.7 % in the earliest scenario (POS1995) and by 6.6 % in the most recent scenario (POS2015) (see Fig. 12). Reduced electricity consumption not only trims production expenses and emissions in the electricity sector but also opens up opportunities for exporting electricity to neighboring countries.

5. Conclusion and policy implications

Energy subsidy reforms in different nations seek to uphold energy security, guarantee the equitable allocation of subsidies, and tackle environmental concerns. Iran, which is home to roughly 1 % of the global population, provides a significant level of subsidies to its energy

sector. As per the International Energy Agency (IEA) in 2023, Iran's subsidies to the electricity industry account for 11.4 % of the total worldwide, with the remaining portion distributed among other countries.

The irregular and rapid growth of electricity consumption in Iran is attributed to the substantial subsidies granted to the sector. With an average annual growth rate of 5 % in Iran's electricity consumption per capita exceeding the global average, persisting on this trajectory stands to yield diverse economic, environmental, and social repercussions. However, this study is limited by not quantitatively assessing the environmental benefits (e.g., CO₂ emission reductions) and social outcomes (e.g., equity) of subsidy reforms. Although these aspects are qualitatively discussed, future research should undertake detailed quantitative evaluations to provide a more comprehensive basis for integrated policy design.

This research adopts a retrospective approach to evaluate the economic ramifications of enacting subsidy reforms in Iran's electricity sector utilizing a state-space model for the period of 1985–2023, alongside assessing the implications of delaying such measures. Sustaining the provision of subsidies will initially foster unsustainable consumption patterns and incentivize the growth of energy-intensive industries. Subsequently, it will result in a continuous decline in the real price of electricity within an economy like Iran's, rendering the implementation of subsidy reforms increasingly challenging.

The state-space model findings indicate that electricity is a commodity with low elasticity in Iran. Persevering with electricity subsidies in the reference scenario has resulted in a gradual reduction in consumer responsiveness, leading to the price elasticity of electricity demand nearing zero in recent years. These conclusions align perfectly with consumer behavior theory, which posits that price elasticity diminishes as real prices decrease. The impact of subsidy reforms within the electricity sector reveals a rise in own-price elasticity alongside a decline in electricity consumption, particularly when compared to the reference scenario. Furthermore, the timelier implementation of subsidy reforms yields a more substantial influence on regulating electricity usage, highlighting a cause-and-effect relationship in this regard.

Subsidy reforms have the potential to influence consumer habits, thereby regulating long-term consumption patterns. Energy subsidies distort market signals for both consumers and producers by introducing artificial price signals. These distortions tend to encourage excessive consumption while simultaneously discouraging efficient production, leading to sustained demand–supply imbalances. Rather than addressing these structural issues, the Iranian government has historically responded by deepening subsidies, which has positioned Iran among the highest subsidizing nations globally.

A key finding of this study is the observed weakening of income elasticity of electricity demand over time. This trend may reflect

Fig. 10. Electricity prices and their elasticity under the different scenarios. (Source: Authors' calculations)

saturation effects, as household access to electrical appliances and cooling technologies reaches a plateau, as well as structural economic shifts, such as declining energy intensity in economic activity or the transition to service-based sectors. This reduced responsiveness to income growth further underscores the urgency of reform: as subsidies persist, consumption becomes increasingly detached from economic fundamentals, locking in inefficient usage patterns.

Therefore, the primary recommendation is to implement early and consistent electricity subsidy reforms. Specifically, a phased reform plan over a five-year period is advised, involving gradual price increases to minimize social shocks. To address potential adverse impacts on vulnerable populations, targeted compensatory measures such as direct cash transfers or electricity vouchers for low-income households are essential. These steps can ensure the affordability of electricity while maintaining the efficiency and sustainability goals of the reform.

Delaying reform not only entrenches inefficiencies but also undermines the effectiveness of future policies by weakening behavioral responsiveness. Timely and well-targeted reforms can achieve fiscal savings, reduce energy waste, and facilitate the adoption of cleaner technologies, paving the way toward a more sustainable and equitable energy system.

Although this study specifically addresses Iran's context, its findings

can be valuable for other oil-dependent countries with similar energy consumption patterns and subsidy policies. However, due to institutional, economic, and political differences, generalization of results should be undertaken cautiously with careful analysis of local conditions. Future research could explore multi-country experiences in energy subsidy reforms and provide a more comprehensive framework to assist policymakers in countries facing similar challenges.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Siab Mamipour: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Validation, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. Mahsa Ghahremani: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Validation, Investigation, Writing–original draft, Writing– review & editing. Ata Malfuzi: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing–review & editing. Seyed Armin Motahar: Conceptualization, Validation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

Fig. 11. The price of electricity versus its elasticity in the earliest (POS1995) and the latest (POS2015) scenarios (Source: Authors' calculations).

Fig. 12. Cumulative electricity consumption and its reduction compared to the reference scenario (Source: Authors' calculations).

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix

Table A1
Literature Overview on Energy Subsidy Reform Classified by Methodological Approaches

Authors	Country	Period	Methodology	Results
[5]	China	2007	CGE	Considerable decline in energy demand and CO2 emissions and adverse effects on GDP and employment.
[6]	Malaysia	2005	CGE	Decreasing the aggregate energy demand, reducing the carbon emissions level, and falling demand for products in the transport sector.
[7]	Abu Dhabi	2007	CGE	Reduction in carbon emissions; rising GDP; the positive effect of reducing electricity subsidies is greater than water subsidies.
[8]	India	2007–2014	CGE	Elimination of cross-subsidies will reduce household incomes in rural areas due to rising inflation.
[9]	Kuwait	2010	CGE	Reduction in carbon dioxide emissions and adverse economic effects; 5 % reduction in GDP and 8 % in household welfare.
[10]	Iran & GCC Nations	2000–2020	CGE + Input-Output Hybrid	Found that cross-subsidies between fuel types create complexity in reform outcomes. Highlighted the significance of structural changes in heavy industries. Welfare loss short term; net gain medium term with correct compensation.
[11]	Iran	1990–2009	CGE	The half-payment scenario is superior to the complete-payment scenario due to its significant environmental, welfare, and economic impacts.
[12]	Iran	1999–2000	CGE	Combined reform has a positive effect on the welfare and reduces the incomes of the poor.
[13]	China	2010	Input-output	The impact of removing energy subsidies are various for different types of energy, and if the subsidies of oil products remove, they have considerable impacts on households.
[36]	Chile	2017–2026	CGE Model	Achieved significant GHG emission reductions (40.4 %–57.5 %) through combined policies. NCRE subsidies mitigated social impacts and supported household income. Minimal GDP loss (0.3 %) observed from coal plant phase-outs.
[14]	Algeria	1996–2021	ARDL	A 1 % reduction in fossil fuel subsidies increases renewable energy production by 15.19 % in the long run, with an annual adjustment speed toward equilibrium of 34.05 %.
[15]	Iran	1986–2015	ARDL	The relationship between energy prices and energy intensity is long-term; the Iranian government has been advised to consider industrial reforms and technology improvements before raising energy prices.
[16]	63 developed and developing countries	1982–2009	Panel data	The effects of reforms vary among countries. The results show that factors determining the price-cost margin of electricity and the level of cross-subsidies are electricity consumption, income levels, and the country's specific characteristics.
[17]	Indonesia	1992–2015	Panel data	Reduced electricity consumption: efficiency of electricity consumption improves.
[18]	Kuwait	1980–2008	micro-models	Rising electricity prices reduce its annual consumption by 4741 million kWh. As a result, it compensates for household welfare losses.
[19]	France	2012–2017	Functional State Space Model	Forecasting electricity demand contributes significantly to further resource development, strategic policymaking, energy-mix plans, and acceptance patterns.
[21]	Lesotho	1995–2012	State-space model	Provided that the real price of electricity rises over time, consumer behavior and price sensitivity may change over the long term.
[22]	South Africa	1980–2005	State-space model	Rising electricity prices may lead to a change in consumer sensitivity to price fluctuations.
[25]	China	1991–2009	State-space model	An increase in electricity prices has little effect on energy demand.
[28]	Turkey	1960–2008	State-space model	Rising electricity prices do not significantly affect consumer response because electricity is an essential commodity.
[37]	Iran	2003–2019	ECBA model	Reducing energy subsidies would raise the government income and economic growth in the long-term, in addition to environmental advantages.
[38]	Canada	2009	Lorenz curve and Gini coefficient	In the subsidized electricity market, high-income households consume more energy resources; governments can move to a pricing structure based on an integrated market to tackle this problem.
[39]	Iran	1990–2013	Translog cost model	In the optimistic hypothesis, raising electricity costs may reduce energy consumption. Alternatively, the pessimistic hypothesis states that energy consumption may rise due to inelastic fuel demand and substantial substitution between fuels.
[40]	China	2017–2021	DEA model	Consumer subsidies negatively impact mine production efficiency (–0.020 influence weight), despite the role of technological advancements. Environmental governance, market competition, and management quality mediate this effect. Reforms like optimizing pricing mechanisms are recommended to mitigate negative impacts and support energy structure adjustments.
[41]	China	2010	price-gap approach	Negative effects on GDP and employment; electricity subsidy reduction strategies are needed to improve efficiency and equality.
[42]	South Africa	2016–2026	Quantitative techno-economic	Advancement of renewable technologies, including wind and solar PV, decreasing demand for fossil fuels, and noteworthy reduction in the cost of electricity generation.
[43]	Jordan	2017–2018	Pearson correlation coefficient	Electricity subsidies promote energy use and limits government budget. So, the government cannot do its socio-economic aims and GHG targets. Moreover, it prevents renewable energy sources and the development of energy efficiency.

Source: Authors' summary

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] Subsidy reforms in the Middle East and north Africa region : a review [Online]. Available: <https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/212631469021941386/subsidy-reforms-in-the-middle-east-and-north-africa-region-a-review>. (Accessed 9 January 2025).
- [2] Fossil fuel subsidies – topics - IEA [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/topics/fossil-fuel-subsidies>. (Accessed 9 January 2025).
- [3] Iran Ministry of Energy (MOE)Tehran, "Energy Balance of Iran in 2017,." EBI. .
- [4] IEA, World energy balances 2020 edition database documentation [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/subscribe-to-data-services/world>, 2020. (Accessed 9 January 2025).
- [5] B. Lin, Z. Jiang, Estimates of energy subsidies in China and impact of energy subsidy reform, *Energy Econ.* 33 (2) (2011) 273–283 [Online]. Available: <https://ideas.repec.org/a/eee/eneeco/v33y2011i2p273-283.html>. (Accessed 9 January 2025).

- [6] S. Solaymani, F. Kari, Impacts of energy subsidy reform on the Malaysian economy and transportation sector, *Energy Policy* 70 (Jul. 2014) 115–125, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2014.03.035>.
- [7] Y. Wang, S. Ali Almazrooei, Z. Kapsalyamova, A. Diabat, I.T. Tsai, Utility subsidy reform in abu Dhabi: a review and a computable general equilibrium analysis, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 55 (Mar. 2016) 1352–1362, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2015.07.099>.
- [8] R. Bhattacharyya, A. Ganguly, Cross subsidy removal in electricity pricing in India, *Energy Policy* 100 (Jan. 2017) 181–190, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2016.10.024>.
- [9] A. Gelan, Economic and environmental impacts of electricity subsidy reform in Kuwait: a general equilibrium analysis, *Energy Policy* 112 (Jan. 2018) 381–398, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2017.10.032>.
- [10] F. Habibi, M.S. Karimi, Foreign direct investment and economic growth: evidence from Iran and GCC, *Iran. Econ. Rev.* 21 (3) (2017) 601–620, <https://doi.org/10.22059/IER.2017.62942>.
- [11] Z. Farajzadeh, M. Bakhshoodeh, Economic and environmental analyses of Iranian energy subsidy reform using Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model, *Energy Sustain. Dev.* 27 (Aug. 2015) 147–154, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ESD.2015.06.002>.
- [12] J. Jensen, D. Tarr, Trade, exchange rate, and energy pricing reform in Iran: potentially large efficiency effects and gains to the poor, *Rev. Dev. Econ.* 7 (4) (2003) 543–562, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9361.00208>.
- [13] Z. Jiang, X. Ouyang, G. Huang, The distributional impacts of removing energy subsidies in China, *China Econ. Rev.* 33 (Apr. 2015) 111–122, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHIECO.2015.01.012>.
- [14] S. Matallah, S. Boudaoud, A. Matallah, M. Ferhaoui, The role of fossil fuel subsidies in preventing a jump-start on the transition to renewable energy: empirical evidence from Algeria, *Resour. Policy* 86 (Oct. 2023) 104276, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RESOURPOL.2023.104276>.
- [15] S. Barkhordari, M. Fattahi, Reform of energy prices, energy intensity and technology: a case study of Iran (ARDL approach), *Energy Strategy Rev.* 18 (Dec. 2017) 18–23, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ESR.2017.09.004>.
- [16] Erdogdu and Erkan, The impact of power market reforms on electricity price-cost margins and cross-subsidy levels: a cross country panel data analysis, *Energy Policy* 39 (3) (2011) 1080–1092 [Online]. Available: <https://ideas.repec.org/a/eee/ene/pol/v39y2011i3p1080-1092.html>. (Accessed 9 January 2025).
- [17] P.J. Burke, S. Kurniawati, Electricity subsidy reform in Indonesia: demand-side effects on electricity use, *Energy Policy* 116 (May 2018) 410–421, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2018.02.018>.
- [18] M.A.M. BuShehri, M.K. Wohlgenant, Measuring the welfare effects of reducing a subsidy on a commodity using micro-models: an application to Kuwait's residential demand for electricity, *Energy Econ.* 34 (2) (Mar. 2012) 419–425, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENERG.2011.08.001>.
- [19] K. Nagbe, J. Cugliari, J. Jacques, Short-term electricity demand forecasting using a functional state space model, *Energies* 11 (5) (2018) 1120, <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN11051120>. May 2018.
- [20] I. Arisoy, I. Ozturk, Estimating industrial and residential electricity demand in Turkey: a time varying parameter approach, *Energy* 66 (Mar. 2014) 959–964, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENERGY.2014.01.016>.
- [21] R.I. Thamae, L.Z. Thamae, T.M. Thamae, Dynamics of electricity demand in Lesotho: a kalman filter approach, *Studies in Business and Economics* 10 (1) (Apr. 2015) 130–139, <https://doi.org/10.1515/SBE-2015-0012>.
- [22] R. Inglesi-Lotz, The evolution of price elasticity of electricity demand in South Africa: a Kalman filter application, *Energy Policy* 39 (6) (2011) 3690–3696, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2011.03.078>.
- [23] B.E. Hansen, Testing for parameter instability in linear models, *J Policy Model* 14 (4) (Aug. 1992) 517–533, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0161-8938\(92\)90019-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0161-8938(92)90019-9).
- [24] A.C. Harvey, Forecasting, structural time series models and the kalman filter, *Forecasting, Structural Time Series Models and the Kalman Filter* (Feb. 1990), <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107049994>.
- [25] G. Tong, Y. Yang, A state-space approach to estimate energy demand model in China, *Energy Proc.* 5 (Jan. 2011) 1177–1181, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2011.03.206>.
- [26] T. Nakajima, S. Hamori, Change in consumer sensitivity to electricity prices in response to retail deregulation: a panel empirical analysis of the residential demand for electricity in the United States, *Energy Policy* 38 (5) (May 2010) 2470–2476, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2009.12.041>.
- [27] Z. Dilaver Zafer, L.C. Hunt, Industrial electricity demand for Turkey: a structural time series analysis, *Energy Econ.* 33 (3) (May 2011) 426–436, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2010.10.001>.
- [28] I. Arisoy, I. Ozturk, Estimating industrial and residential electricity demand in Turkey: a time varying parameter approach, *Energy* 66 (2014) 959–964, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2014.01.016>.
- [29] R.I. Thamae, L.Z. Thamae, T.M. Thamae, Dynamics of electricity demand in Lesotho: a kalman filter approach, *Studies in Business and Economics* 10 (1) (2015) 130–139, <https://doi.org/10.1515/sbe-2015-0012>.
- [30] PRGIRI, “Law of the Second Five-Year Economic, Social and Cultural Development Plan of the Islamic Republic of Iran. Available from:” Parliament research center of the Islamic Republic of Iran. [Online]. Available: <https://rc.majlis.ir/fa/law/show/92488> (in Persian).
- [31] M.H. Pesaran, Y. Shin, R.J. Smith, Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships, *J. Appl. Econom.* 16 (3) (May 2001) 289–326, <https://doi.org/10.1002/JAE.616>.
- [32] P.K. Adom, W. Bekoe, Conditional dynamic forecast of electrical energy consumption requirements in Ghana by 2020: a comparison of ARDL and PAM, *Energy* 44 (1) (2012) 367–380, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2012.06.020>.
- [33] National accounts of Iran [Online]. Available: <https://cbi.ir/page/2072.aspx>. (Accessed 19 May 2025).
- [34] Ministry of energy | Iran data portal [Online]. Available: <https://irandataportal.syr.edu/ministry-of-energy>. (Accessed 19 May 2025).
- [35] Z. Jia, B. Lin, The impact of removing cross subsidies in electric power industry in China: welfare, economy, and CO2 emission, *Energy Policy* 148 (Jan) (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2020.111994>.
- [36] C. Mardones, Contribution of the carbon tax, phase-out of thermoelectric power plants, and renewable energy subsidies for the decarbonization of Chile – A CGE model and microsimulations approach, *J Environ Manage* 352 (Feb. 2024) 120017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JENVMAN.2024.120017>.
- [37] S.-P. Motlagh, M.M. Farsiabi, An environmental & economic analysis for reducing energy subsidies, *Int. J. Environ. Res.* 1 (2) (Apr. 2007) 150–162, <https://doi.org/10.22059/IJER.2010.121>.
- [38] S.R. Mirnezami, Electricity inequality in Canada: should pricing reforms eliminate subsidies to encourage efficient usage? *Util. Policy* 31 (Dec. 2014) 36–43, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JUP.2014.08.001>.
- [39] Hossein Mirshojaeian Hosseini, Vahid Majed, Shinji Kaneko, The effects of energy subsidy reform on fuel demand in Iran, *Money and Economy* 29 (10) (Apr. 2015) 23–44. <http://noo.rs/nJNzQ>. (Accessed 9 January 2025).
- [40] X. Wang, L. Xu, Q. Gao, N. Liu, C. Wang, K. Li, Effect of consumer subsidies on coal mine efficiency and its transmission mechanism, *Energy Policy* 196 (Jan. 2025) 114412, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2024.114412>.
- [41] X. Wang and B. Lin, “Electricity subsidy reform in China,” <https://doi.org/10.1177/0958305X16681681>, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 245–262, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.1177/0958305X16681681.
- [42] T.S. Schmidt, T. Matsuo, A. Michaelowa, Renewable energy policy as an enabler of fossil fuel subsidy reform? Applying a socio-technical perspective to the cases of South Africa and Tunisia, *Glob. Environ. Change* 45 (Jul. 2017) 99–110, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GLOENVCHA.2017.05.004>.
- [43] A. Albatayneh, A. Juaidi, R. Abdallah, A. Peña-Fernández, F. Manzano-Agugliaro, Effect of the subsidised electrical energy tariff on the residential energy consumption in Jordan, *Energy Rep.* 8 (Nov. 2022) 893–903, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EGYR.2021.12.019>.